

Single-component upconverting polymeric nanoparticles

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Abstract

Low-power light upconversion is a highly desirable feature for a broad range of applications and new materials enabling this process are sought in both bulk and particulate form. Here, we report the preparation of upconverting nanoparticles from a methacrylic terpolymer bearing diphenylanthracene and meso-phenoxytris(heptyl)porphyrin pendant groups by micro-emulsion technique. The use of a terpolymer in which the upconverting dye molecules are covalently attached mitigates some of the drawbacks of TTA-UC nanoparticles made by other techniques, in particular dye leakage from the nanoparticles, and limited control of the sensitizer and emitter concentration within each nanoparticle. We investigated size and morphology of the new upconverting nanoparticles by dynamic light scattering and transmission electron microscopy and elucidated their upconverting properties by luminescence spectroscopy.

FIGURE FOR ToC_ABSTRACT

1. Introduction

Polymer-based materials possessing the ability to upconvert low-power light by triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA-UC) have recently garnered increasing attention due to their potential application in improving solar cell technology or bioimaging.^[1, 2] TTA-UC is a photochemical process that uses a two-dye system to emit anti-Stokes-shifted light. A sensitizer harvests a photon that after intersystem crossing populates a triplet level, before triplet-triplet energy transfer to an emitter molecule occurs. The annihilation of two emitter triplet excited states eventually produces a singlet excited state, which (if relaxation occurs radiatively) leads to the emission of one photon of higher energy.^[1, 3]

Initially studied in solution,^[4, 5] TTA-UC dye pairs were recently introduced into polymer systems, e.g. in rubbery polymers^[6, 7], polymer glasses^[8-10] and organogels^[11]. Concomitantly, the preparation of upconverting nano-objects based on TTA-UC has undergone a rapid development in the past five years.^[12-21] This development was in part fueled by the realization that these nano-objects bear great potential for bioimaging technology. As the scattering of light is less significant at longer wavelengths, the use of upconverting nanoparticles leads to reduced scattering in complex media. The prospect of utilizing dyes capable of upconverting near-IR light in UC-nanoparticles is particularly attractive, as it would allow for autofluorescence suppression, greater tissue penetration and reduce photodamage to the tissue.^[22] Compared to inorganic UC-nanoparticles doped with rare-earth elements,^[23,24] organic dye-based TTA-UC systems benefit from a higher extinction coefficient and therefore typically require lower excitation power densities. Micellar structures made of a α -tocopheryl sebacate surfactant were reported to stabilize a meso-tetraphenyl-tetrabenzoporphine palladium/perylene dye pair in aqueous media and cause the formation of self-assemblies with a diameter of ~ 30 nm showing UC emission under low excitation power densities (down to $10 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$).^[12] Landfester,

Balushev and coworkers reported the preparation of nanocapsules via emulsion polymerization in which sensitizer and emitter molecules were solubilized in a liquid hexadecane core. These capsules show efficient upconversion in aqueous suspensions and were used for cells imaging.^[13] Capsules were also prepared using microfluidics in combination with photopolymerization of a polymeric shell around a liquid core containing UC chromophores.^[25] Photochemical production of hydroxyl radical with upconverting capsules was also demonstrated using blue-shifted emission originating from green light excitation.^[26] Polymeric cross-linked nanoparticles dyed with sensitizer/emitter systems were also reported by Monguzzi *et al.* and our group.^[15, 16] Recently, silica nanoparticles containing sensitizer/emitter system were synthesized and used for *in vivo* and *in vitro* bioimaging.^[14, 27] In that case, the sensitizer/emitter pair was first stabilized by an amphiphilic polymer *via* hydrophobic interactions, and a silica shell was then grown around the micelles thus formed. However, for some applications, it might be suitable to increase the chromophore content inside the particles. Covalent attachment for the UC dyes to a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) backbone was recently proposed as strategy to avoid phase segregation of palladium octaethylporphyrin (PdOEP) and diphenylanthracene (DPA) even at high concentration into glassy materials.^[10] It has been shown that polymeric solid-state materials allow for good dispersion of the sensitizer and the emitter controlling precisely their concentration to tune UC properties.^[6-8, 28] Capitalizing on these findings, we explored the possibility to create nanoparticles from a methacrylic terpolymer bearing pendant DPA emitter and meso-phenoxytris(heptyl)porphyrin-ethylmethacrylate (PdmPH3PMA) sensitizer groups. Nanoparticles made of this sensitizer and emitter-containing terpolymer were prepared by a microemulsion technique (**Figure 1**). The design approach appears to mitigate some of the drawbacks of existing TTA-UC nanoparticles. No organic-solvent-based liquid core with potentially hazardous impact on biological systems is used to disperse the UC-dyes and the covalent tethering of the chromophores to the polymeric

backbone alleviates the risks of dye leakage, phase segregation and ensures a constant composition of the luminescent probe overtime. The size distribution and morphology of the resulting particles was characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Their upconverting properties were confirmed by luminescence spectroscopy. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first example where UC dyes are incorporated into the molecular architecture and allow the formation of stable nanoparticles made of a single-component polymer core. Therefore, this system can be used as a model to study confinement of dispersed dyes into nanoparticulate environment avoiding relaxation into a phase-segregated state over time, thanks to the glassy nature of the material at ambient and physiological temperature. Parameters such as intermolecular distance between the emitters and the sensitizer can therefore be considered as constant over time and mainly dependent on dye concentration incorporation to the polymer backbone.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials

Poly(methyl methacrylate) (weight-average molecular weight, M_w , = 120,000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, Aldrich), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, Sigma Aldrich) and dichloromethane (DCM, Sigma Aldrich) were used as received. The synthesis of the copolymer poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) was previously reported (DPA content = 30 wt%, PdmPH3P Content = 0.045 wt%, number-average molecular weight, M_n , = 120,000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, Dispersity, D , = 1.7).^[10]

2.2. Nanoparticle Preparation

A representative procedure is provided for the preparation of nanoparticles using a micro-emulsion technique. The copolymer poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) (25 mg) was dissolved into DCM (1.9 mL) and the solution was combined with an aqueous SDS solution (5 mL, 3 mg·mL⁻¹). The mixture was stirred for 5 min in order to form a pre-emulsion and sonicated for 10 min using a Hielscher sonicator UP 400S with 0.5 pulse·sec⁻¹ (cycles of 0.5 sec pulse and 0.5 sec delay, actual sonication time was 5 min) and a 60 % intensity. The organic solvent was then removed by gently stirring the suspension at 60 °C for 2 h. Finally, the volume of the suspension was adjusted to 5 mL with additional milli-Q water to obtain a concentration of 5 mg·mL⁻¹. The reference PMMA nanoparticles were prepared following the same procedure.

2.3. Characterization of Poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) Nanoparticles

2.3.1. Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Aliquots of the original nanoparticle dispersion (0.25 mL, 5 mg·mL⁻¹) were diluted by adding milli-Q water (2 mL) to obtain dispersions with a concentration of ~0.56 mg·mL⁻¹, which were filtered through 0.45 µm PVDF filters into cylindrical glass cells with a diameter of 10 mm. Light-scattering measurements were performed with a 3D LS Spectrometer (LS Instruments AG, Switzerland) equipped with linearly polarized and collimated laser beam operating at 660 nm. The measurements were performed at scattering angles of 45°, 90° and 135° for 180 s at a temperature of 25 °C. The correlation function from DLS was fitted to a Schulz-Zimm distribution^[29,30] to obtain a polydispersity index (std/mean) and a mean diffusion coefficient. The average particle hydrodynamic radius was determined from the mean diffusion coefficient using the Einstein-Stokes relation. Number-weighted distribution was obtained assuming solid-sphere morphology of the particles as observed by TEM (see details in Supporting Information).

2.3.2. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The size and morphology of the poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles were further characterized by TEM. Typically, one drop of sample suspension ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was placed onto a carbon-film-coated 300-mesh copper grid (CF-300-Cu, Electron Microscopy Sciences) and was allowed to dry under ambient condition for overnight. Images were recorded using a FEI Tecnai Spirit microscope with an operating voltage of 120 kV and a Valeta camera (Olympus SIS) with an image resolution of 2048×2048 pixels. The TEM images of the PMMA reference nanoparticles were recorded on a Philips CM100 transmission electron microscope operating at 80 kV and a Morada camera (Olympus SIS). The micrographs were examined with ImageJ software (1.46r, <http://imagej.nih.gov/ij>) and the nanoparticles average size was determined manually by measuring the diameter of 200 particles from more than ten regions of the grid.

2.3.3. Optical Experiments

Upconverted fluorescence of aqueous suspensions of the poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was produced by exciting the upconverting sample with a continuous-wave diode laser operating at 532 nm (TECGL-50 mW from General Microtechnology and Photonics, Switzerland) equipped with a laser line filter (532 nm, FWHM = 10 nm, FL532-10 from Thorlabs). A $1/e^2$ beam diameter of 0.798 mm was determined by a knife-edge method assuming a Gaussian shape for the beam profile. The excitation power density was varied using a continuously variable neutral density filter (NDC-50C-2M-A from Thorlabs) and was measured with an optical power meter (Thorlabs PM100USB with

photodiode power sensor S120VC). Steady-state photoluminescence (PL) experiments were performed in an QS Quartz SUPRASIL[®] (length pass = 1 mm, volume = 350 μ L from Hellma[®] Analytics) using a Photon Technology International (PTI) C720 spectrophotometer equipped with a Hamamatsu R928P photomultiplier and a notch filter (532 nm, OD>4 from Edmund Optics). The sample was excited at an incident angle of 70° to the quartz cuvette surface and the photoluminescence was detected with an angle of 30° between the excitation and the detection. Direct fluorescence emission spectrum of DPA moieties was recorded by exciting the aqueous suspension of the poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles (5 mg·mL⁻¹) at 355 nm using the Xe arc lamp of the same spectrophotometer equipped with a 400 nm long pass filter (FGL400 from Thorlabs) on the detection side. The angle between the excitation and the detection was 90° and the incidence angle of the excitation light source with respect to the quartz cuvette surface was 45°. Ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) absorption spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometer and same cuvettes as for photoluminescence experiments were used (length pass = 1 mm).

3. Results and Discussion

The synthesis of the sensitizer- and emitter-containing poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) terpolymer via free-radical copolymerization of methyl methacrylate (MMA), with methacrylic monomers carrying the DPA (emitter) and PdmPH3P (sensitizer) motifs was previously reported by our group.^[10] The photophysical properties of the metallo-porphyrin/diphenylanthracene dye pair have extensively been studied^[1,31,32] and the bulk properties of a series of poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) terpolymers were investigated in detail.^[10] Thus, this well-investigated model system appeared to be useful to probe energy-transfer processes in the targeted nanostructured materials. Nanoparticles were

prepared by a micro-emulsion method, using a terpolymer with 1:1,616:10,423 PdmPH3PMA:DPAMA:MMA ratio ($M_n = 120,000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $D = 1.7$) (**Figure 1**). This composition was chosen as this M_n was commercially available for the control PMMA and the solid-state upconverting properties were good.^[10] The terpolymer was dissolved in DCM and emulsified in the presence of an aqueous solution of sodium dodecyl sulfate, before the organic solvent was removed by evaporation. The particle size and morphology were determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and the size distribution was confirmed by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The electron micrographs show polydisperse spherical particles with an average diameter of ca. 98 nm, most of which can be seen to aggregate in small clusters (**Figures 2, 3B**). The DLS measurements reveal an average hydrodynamic radius of 124 nm, a polydispersity of 0.31, but no larger aggregates (**Table 1, Figure 3A**), which supports the conclusion that the aggregates observed in the TEM images are the result of drying effects during sample preparation. The particle size distribution functions were obtained by measuring the diameter of the particles seen in the TEM images (**Figures 2 and 3B**) and by converting the intensity-weighted DLS size distribution into a number-weighted distribution by assuming a solid sphere morphology of the particles (**Figure 3A, Supporting Information**), which is supported by the TEM images. Gratifyingly, similar size distributions were obtained with those two techniques.

For reference purposes, we also prepared PMMA nanoparticles using the same micro-emulsion method. Also in this case, TEM images display polydisperse spherical particles, while DLS experiments revealed a mean hydrodynamic radius of 91 nm and a polydispersity of 0.37 (**Table 1, Supporting Information Figure S1**). The TEM images of such PMMA nanoparticles show a lower contrast than the upconverting nanoparticles (**Supporting Information Figure S1**), which can be rationalized by the lack of electron-dense aromatic rings and the heavy metal ions. The similar mean hydrodynamic diameter of the PMMA and poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-

PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles suggests that the presence of the DPA and PdmPH3P groups does not exert a major impact on the particle formation process, at least under the conditions employed here.

The upconverted photoluminescence of the new nanoparticles was investigated by exciting aqueous suspensions with a continuous-wave diode laser operating at 532 nm. A laserline filter at 532 ± 10 nm was used on the excitation side and a notch filter 532 ± 10 nm ($OD > 4$) was positioned on the detection side in order to suppress excitation light scattered by the particles. A continuously variable neutral density filter was used to adjust the power density from 0.25 to $5.94 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ without prior deoxygenation. A clear anti-Stokes-shifted blue emission with spectral characteristics that are characteristic of the DPA motif could be observed for excitation power densities greater than $0.51 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (**Figures 4 and 5**). A double-logarithmic plot of the integrated UC emission intensity versus the average excitation power density shows data that fit to a linear function with a slope of 1.74 and 1.05 in the lower and higher excitation power regimes, respectively. The presence of quadratic regime, where relaxation pathways of the DPA triplets other than TTA are dominant, and a linear regime, where the annihilation route becomes the dominant decay pathway, is well documented for TTA-UC process.^[1] As discussed in a previous contribution on the UC properties of films made from the same terpolymer, porphyrin desymmetrization led to a change in its molecular conformation that further affected the match between the energy levels of the sensitizer and the emitter.^[10] The presence of a pronounced emission peak associated with porphyrin phosphorescence (Supporting Information **Figure S3**) reveals that alternate relaxation pathways compete with the annihilation of triplet excited emitters due to non-efficient energy transfer between the porphyrin and the DPA or from back-transfer. Another important non-radiative relaxation pathway is likely quenching of the triplet excited states with O_2 .^[1] With reference to possible applications in biosensing, we omitted deoxygenation of the samples *via* sparging with argon, but also note that this process proved

difficult due to foaming (probably triggered by the surfactant present). Additionally, the glassy nature of the polymer might limit Dexter-type energy transfers in the particles, particularly during the annihilation step. Moreover, scattering of incident light by the nanoparticles reduces the power density that is available for absorption by the sensitizer. This scattering effect can be observed in the absorption spectrum of the nanoparticles (Supporting Information **Figure S4**) and limits the absorption of the porphyrin as opposed to that observed for the same polymer in an organic solvent as reported in the previous work on the UC films.^[10] These explanations are consistent with the relatively high excitation density ($> 0.51 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) required to trigger the anti-Stokes emission from the UC nanoparticles (**Figure 5**). The characteristic emission spectral motif of DPA moieties were also obtained by direct excitation of the poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles suspension at 355 nm using a Xe arc lamp (Supporting Information **Figure S5**) and a 400 nm long pass filter was used on the detection side in order to filter out the scattered and reflected excitation light. Moreover, photoluminescent (Supporting Information **Figure S3**) and absorption (Supporting Information **Figure S4**) experiments performed on control PMMA nanoparticles show that they do not have optical properties which could interfere with the sensitizer/emitter dye system. Gratifyingly, excitation of the upconverting nanoparticles suspension at a power density of $2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for 2 hours caused negligible UC maximum intensity variations, which indicates a good stability of the particles towards photobleaching (Supporting Information **Figure S2**). This system can therefore serve as a starting point to develop well-defined single-component nanoparticles with higher UC efficiency by choosing carefully the polymer matrix and the chromophore system.

4. Conclusions

In summary, nanoparticles made from poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) terpolymers were prepared by a micro-emulsion method. Both size and morphology of the particles were characterized by TEM and DLS and were found to be similar to those of control nanoparticles made from neat PMMA. Aqueous nanoparticle suspensions showed blue upconverted emission with spectral features that are typical for the system at hand and was observed at incident power densities of $0.51 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ or greater. The observed residual phosphorescence points to a rather moderate quantum efficiency for the overall process. Although the latter is hard to determine as the scattering of the excitation light by the particles limits the light which can be absorbed by the sensitizer. Interestingly, the luminescent properties were stable over several days and also the size and the morphology of the particles remained unchanged. The high optical and colloidal stability of the nanoparticles is desirable for further applications, and we speculate that the design principles presented here will be particularly useful in the design of next generation UC nanoparticles for bioimaging.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author. The authors thank Roberto Vadrucci for the helpful comments and discussions.

Acknowledgements: The authors thank the Swiss National Science Foundation (grants number 200020_152968 and PP00P2133597/1) and the Adolphe Merkle Foundation for the financial support.

Received: Month XX, XXXX; Revised: Month XX, XXXX; Published online:

DOI: 10.1002/marc.((insert number)) ((or ppap., mabi., macp., mame., mren., mats.))

Keywords: (nanoparticles, copolymers, upconversion, luminescence, dyes)

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of the preparation of terpolymer-based upconverting nanoparticles.

Figure 2. Representative TEM images of poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles that had been drop-cast from an aqueous dispersion ($c = 5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) onto a TEM grid.

Table 1. Summary of the hydrodynamic diameter and polydispersity of nanoparticles made from the poly(DPAMA-*co*-MA-*co*-PdmPH3PMA) terpolymer and PMMA (reference).

Polymer	Hydrodynamic diameter D_H [nm]^b	Polydispersity (std/mean)^b
PMMA	91	0.37
Poly(DPAMA- <i>co</i> -MA- <i>co</i> -PdmPH3PMA)	124	0.31

Figure 3. Size distributions of poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles measured (A) in an aqueous suspension with a concentration of $\sim 0.56 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ by DLS at a scattering angle of 90° (the data was converted to number-weighted distribution by assuming solid-sphere morphology) and (B) by evaluation of transmission electron microscopy images; the sample had been drop-cast from an aqueous nanoparticle dispersion ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) on a TEM grid and air-dried.

Figure 4. Picture showing the upconverted blue emission (visualized through a 500 nm short-pass filter) of a poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticle suspension in water ($5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) excited with a Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm. A magnification of the upconverted light emitted by the suspension at the location of the laser spot is shown in the inset.

Figure 5. (A) Upconverted emission spectra of an aqueous poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) nanoparticles suspension (5 mg·mL⁻¹). (B) Integrated emission intensity of the upconversion spectra as function of the excitation power density. A double-logarithmic plot of the integrated UC emission intensity versus the average excitation power density shows data that fit to a linear function with a slope of 1.74 and 1.05 in the lower and higher excitation power regimes, respectively.